

1 Supplementary Material

2 Table SMI. Literature records of *Solenopsis* from Patagonia.

Locality	Species cited as:	Identified species	Reference
Section I: Previously published records revised and verified in the present study.			
San Pablo, Valdes Peninsula, Chubut	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>	<i>Solenopsis parva</i>	Cheli et al. 2010
El Centro, Valdes Peninsula, Chubut	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>	<i>Solenopsis parva</i>	Cheli et al. 2010
El Centro, Valdes Peninsula, Chubut	<i>Solenopsis</i> sp. 1	<i>Solenopsis metanotalis</i>	Cheli et al. 2010
El Progreso, Valdes Peninsula, Chubut	<i>Solenopsis</i> sp. 1	<i>Solenopsis metanotalis</i>	Cheli et al. 2010
San Pablo, Valdes Peninsula, Chubut	<i>Solenopsis</i> sp. 1	<i>Solenopsis metanotalis</i>	Cheli et al. 2010
El Centro, Valdes Peninsula, Chubut	<i>Solenopsis</i> sp. 1	<i>Solenopsis parva</i>	Cheli et al. 2010
Curruhué Chico Lake, Neuquén	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>	<i>Solenopsis germaini</i>	Fernani et al. 2025
Traful lake, Neuquén	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>	<i>Solenopsis germaini</i>	Fernani et al. 2025
8 km W of Mascardi lake	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>	<i>Solenopsis germaini</i>	Fernani et al. 2025
Route 40, Neuquén	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>	<i>Solenopsis germaini</i>	Fernani et al. 2025
Las Bayas, Río Negro	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>	<i>Solenopsis llanquinensis</i>	Fernani et al. 2025
Route 23, 20 km W of Comallo	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>	<i>Solenopsis llanquinensis</i>	Fernani et al. 2025
Route 237, Neuquén	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>	<i>Solenopsis parva</i>	Fernani et al. 2025
Curruhué Chico Lake, Neuquén	<i>Solenopsis</i> sp. 1	<i>Solenopsis germaini</i>	Fernani et al. 2025
Piedra Pintada, Neuquén	<i>Solenopsis</i> sp. 1	<i>Solenopsis llanquinensis</i>	Fernani et al., 2025
Route 50, Neuquén	<i>Solenopsis</i> sp. 1	<i>Solenopsis metanotalis</i>	Fernani et al. 2025
Collón Curá river, Neuquén	<i>Solenopsis</i> sp. 1	<i>Solenopsis metanotalis</i>	Fernani et al. 2025
Route 49, Neuquén	<i>Solenopsis</i> sp. 1	<i>Solenopsis metanotalis</i>	Fernani et al. 2025
Route 237, Neuquén	<i>Solenopsis</i> sp. 1	<i>Solenopsis metanotalis</i>	Fernani et al. 2025
Catan Lil, Neuquén	<i>Solenopsis</i> sp. 1	<i>Solenopsis parva</i>	Fernani et al. 2025
Catan Lil, Neuquén	<i>Solenopsis</i> sp. 1	<i>Solenopsis metanotalis</i>	Fernani et al. 2025
Koluel Kayke, Santa Cruz	<i>Solenopsis</i> sp 1	<i>Solenopsis metanotalis</i>	Lescano et al. 2017
Pico Truncado, Santa Cruz	<i>Solenopsis</i> sp 1	<i>Solenopsis metanotalis</i>	Lescano et al. 2017

Valle Hermoso, Chubut	<i>Solenopsis</i> sp 2	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>	Lescano et al. 2017
Koluel Kayke, Santa Cruz	<i>Solenopsis</i> sp 3	<i>Solenopsis llanquinensis</i>	Lescano et al. 2017
Esquel, Chubut	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>	<i>Solenopsis germaini</i>	Pereda Gomez et al. 2020
Villa Llanquin, Río Negro	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>	<i>Solenopsis llanquinensis</i>	Pirk, 2014
Villa Llanquin, Río Negro	<i>Solenopsis</i> sp.1	<i>Solenopsis germaini</i>	Pirk, 2014
Villa Llanquin, Río Negro	<i>Solenopsis</i> sp.1	<i>Solenopsis metanotalis</i>	Pirk, 2014
Foyel, Río Negro	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>	<i>Solenopsis germaini</i>	Sasal, 2009
Pilcaniyeu, Río Negro	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>	<i>Solenopsis germaini</i>	Sasal, 2009
Cuesta del Ternero, Río Negro	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>	<i>Solenopsis germaini</i>	Sasal, 2009
Los Moscos, Río Negro	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>	<i>Solenopsis germaini</i>	Sasal, 2009
Los Moscos, Río Negro	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>	<i>Solenopsis parva</i>	Sasal, 2009
Foyel, Río Negro	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>	<i>Solenopsis parva</i>	Sasal, 2009

Section II: Previously published records not examined here.

Tromen lake, provincia de Neuquén	<i>Solenopsis germaini</i>		Pacheco & Mackay 2013
Tte. Gral. Eustoquio Frías, Río Negro	<i>Solenopsis metanotalis</i>		Santschi, 1916
Tte. Gral. Eustoquio Frías, Río Negro	<i>Solenopsis parva</i>		Santschi, 1916
Camarones, Chubut	<i>Solenopsis parva</i>		Emery, 1906:
Puerto Madryn, Chubut	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>		Emery, 1906:
San Martin de los Andes, Neuquén	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>		Kusnezov, 1959
Aluminé lake, Neuquén	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>		Kusnezov, 1959
Quila Quina, Neuquén	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>		Kusnezov, 1959
Pucará, Neuquén	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>		Kusnezov, 1959
Huam-Hum, Neuquén	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>		Kusnezov, 1959
Huechulafquen lake, Neuquén	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>		Kusnezov, 1959
Victoria island, Neuquén	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>		Kusnezov, 1959
Otto Hill, Río Negro	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>		Kusnezov, 1959
Treból lake, Río Negro	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>		Kusnezov, 1959
El Bolsón, Río Negro	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>		Kusnezov, 1959
Epuayén, Chubut	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>		Kusnezov, 1959
Esquel, Chubut	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>		Kusnezov, 1959
Futalaufquen lake, Chubut	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>		Kusnezov, 1959
Krueger lake, Chubut	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>		Kusnezov, 1959
Menéndez Lake, Chubut	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>		Kusnezov, 1959
Valdés Península, Chubut	<i>Solenopsis patagonica</i>		Martínez et al. 2018
Valdés Península, Chubut	<i>Solenopsis schilleri</i>		Martínez et al. 2018

 Section III: New records based solely on material examined in the present study.

Bariloche, Río Negro	<i>Solenopsis germaini</i>
El Bolsón, Río Negro	<i>Solenopsis germaini</i>
Villa La Angostura, Neuquén	<i>Solenopsis germaini</i>
Puerto Blest, Neuquén	<i>Solenopsis germaini</i>
Alto Río Percy, Chubut	<i>Solenopsis germaini</i>
INTA, Río Mayo, Chubut	<i>Solenopsis llanquinensis</i>
Collón Cura river, Neuquén	<i>Solenopsis metanotalis</i>
Mascardi lake, Río Negro	<i>Solenopsis metanotalis</i>
Nilson river, Chubut	<i>Solenopsis metanotalis</i>
Los Tamarisco, Chubut	<i>Solenopsis metanotalis</i>
Gobernador Gregores, Santa Cruz	<i>Solenopsis metanotalis</i>
Villa Regina, Río Negro	<i>Solenopsis parva</i>

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6 **SM II. Type material of *Solenopsis***

7 *Solenopsis germaini*. Emery, 1895

8 Primary type material: syntype workers (number not stated). Primary type locality: Chile:
9 Cordillera de Chillan (*P. Germain*). Primary type depository: MSNG. Examined material
10 was compared with photograph of type material: **CASENT0904632. AntWeb. Version**
11 **8.114. California Academy of Science, online at <https://www.antweb.org>. Accessed**
12 **2025.**

13 *Solenopsis metanotalis* Emery, 1896

14 Primary type material: lectotype worker (by designation of [Pacheco & Mackay, 2013](#):
15 228). Primary type locality: lectotype Argentina: La Plata (*C. Spegazzini*). Primary type
16 depository: MSNG. Examined material was compared with photograph of type material:
17 **CASENT0916026 1 worker, syntype, coll. G. Mayr; CASENT 0103208 1 worker,**
18 **syntype, coll. C. Bruch. AntWeb. Version 8.114. California Academy of Science, online**
19 **at <https://www.antweb.org>. Accessed 2025.**

20 *Solenopsis parva*

21 Primary type material: worker. Primary type locality: Argentina: Mendoza, xii.1865-
22 iii.1866 (*P. Strobel*). Primary type depository: NHMW. Examined material syntype material
23 was compared with photograph of type material: **CASENT0908810. *Solenopsis angulata***
24 **r. *huasanensis* Forel. Coll. A. Forel. Lectotype by Pacheco & Mackay 2013; AntWeb.**
25 **Version 8.114. California Academy of Science, online at <https://www.antweb.org>.**
26 **Accessed 2025.**

27 *Solenopsis patagonica*

28 Primary type material: lectotype worker ([Pacheco & Mackay, 2013](#): 254). Primary type
29 locality: lectotype Argentina: Chubut, Puerto Madryn. Deposited in MSNG. Examined
30 material was compared with photograph of type material: **CASENT0908841 and**
31 **CASENT0913915, coll. A. Forel; CASENT0103221, coll. K. Wolffhuegel. AntWeb.**
32 **Version 8.114. California Academy of Science, online at <https://www.antweb.org>.**
33 **Accessed 2025.**

34 *Solenopsis schilleri*

35 Primary type material: Primary type material: holotype worker. Primary type locality:
36 Argentina: Neuquén, Challacito (*Schiller*). Primary type depository: NHMB. Examined
37 material was compared with photograph of type material: **CASENT0103213. Holotype**
38 **coll. Sanstchi. AntWeb. Version 8.114. California Academy of Science, online at**
39 **<https://www.antweb.org>. Accessed 2025.**

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